

Synthesis of Benzamidothiosemicarbazides and Thiosemicarbazones*

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Several benzamidothiosemicarbazides and the corresponding thiosemicarbazones have been synthesised to evaluate their antitubercular, antibacterial, and antiviral activity.

Since the initial report by Domagk¹ that certain aromatic aldehydethiosemicarbazones possessed high antitubercular activity, numerous aliphatic, aromatic, and heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones²⁻⁶ have been synthesised and tested as potential antituberculous agents. It is of interest that among this group of compounds are substances active against vaccinia virus both in embryonated eggs and in mice.⁷ Thiosemicarbazides in addition to yielding many active tuberculostats also have a protective effect in mice, infected with influenza.⁸ Recent studies have shown that certain long-chain thiosemicarbazones may be effective as potential anticancer and antiviral agents⁹.

The present communication describes the synthesis of three benzamidothiosemicarbazides, obtained by treating successively the acid hydrazide, prepared by the hydrazinolysis of the acid methyl ester, with carbon disulphide, sodium monochloroacetate, and hydrazine hydrate. Thiosemicarbazides have been condensed with various aromatic aldehydes and one heterocyclic aldehyde to furnish the desired thiosemicarbazones.

The screening of these compounds has been done at the Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acid hydrazides were prepared by refluxing a mixture of the methyl ester (1*M*) of the appropriate acid and hydrazine hydrate (1.5*M* 99/100%) for 5 hrs.

* This paper was presented at the 2nd Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society, held at Allahabad in December, 1964.

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Benzamidothiosemicarbazides.—The appropriate acid hydrazide (1.0M) was suspended in liquor ammonia (d. 0.88; 200 ml) and CS₂ (45 ml), cooled to 0°, was added with stirring and 15-ml portions. The temperature of the reaction mixture was kept below 30° by external cooling. Ethanol (100 ml, 95%) was then introduced into the flask. An additional 30 ml of CS₂ was added, followed by 100 ml of ethanol. Stirring was continued for 1 hr. after the additions were completed. An aqueous solution of sodium monochloroacetate (1M) was then added when the mixture became exothermic. To the warm solution 99–100% hydrazine hydrate (60 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate heated on a water bath for 2 hrs. It was concentrated to one-half of its volume and cooled. The desired thiosemicarbazide separated as a white crystalline solid. It was filtered and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. The m.p.s., analyses, and other data relating to the three thiosemicarbazides thus prepared are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
4-Benzamidothiosemicarbazides

No.	Ar.	M.P.	Yield	Formula	% Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	Phenyl	210°	60%	C ₈ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	27.10	26.67
2.	2-hydroxyphenyl	200–201°	70	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	24.89	24.73
3.	3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl	206–207°	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	18.45	18.66

*Melting points are uncorrected.

1-Phenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazones.—The appropriate thiosemicarbazide (0.04M) was dissolved in a hot mixture of glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and ethanol (1:4) and refluxed. To the above refluxing solution, an appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.04M), dissolved in ethanol (10 ml), was added. The contents of the flask were refluxed on a water bath for 2–4 hrs. In most of the cases crystals usually began to separate immediately on cooling; the crystals were then filtered and recrystallised. In a few cases some solvent had to be removed by distillation to facilitate crystallisation. The analytical data and m.p.s of these compounds are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II
1-Phenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazones

No.	R ₂	R ₁ —CONHNH—C—NHN=CHR ₂		Formula	% Nitrogen	
		M.P.*	*Solvent for Crystallisation		Found	Reqd.
		R ₁ = Phenyl.				
1.	Phenyl	177°	A	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	19.17	18.79
2.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	209°	A+D	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	17.34	17.63
3.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	195–96°	A+D	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	17.49	17.83
4.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	225–26°	A+D	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	17.92	17.83
5.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	201°	D+E	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	16.48	16.28
6.	2-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	197–99°	D+E	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	15.85	16.28
7.	2-Methoxyphenyl	190°	D+E	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	16.76	17.07
8.	4-Methoxyphenyl	200°	D+E	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	17.16	17.07

TABLE II (contd.)

1-Phenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazones

No.	R ₂	M.P.	*Solvent for Crystallisation.	Formula	%Nitrogen Found	%Nitrogen Reqd.
Cryst from I. R ₁ —Ph						
9.	2-Chlorophenyl	185-86°	D+E	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₄ ClS	17.19	16.85
10.	3-Chlorophenyl	210-11°	D+E	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₄ ClS	17.20	16.85
11.	4-Chlorophenyl	205°	D+E	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₄ ClS	16.52	16.85
12.	2-Nitrophenyl	198-99°	D+E	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₅ S	20.84	20.41
13.	3-Nitrophenyl	203-04°	D+E	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₅ S	20.68	20.41
14.	3,4-Dioxymethylenephenyl	188°	D+E	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	15.92	16.98
15.	2-Furyl	198-07°	D+E	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ S	16.95	16.45
II. R ₁ = 2-hydroxyphenyl						
16.	Phenyl	185-88°	A	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	17.95	17.33
17.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	201°	A	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	16.78	16.97
18.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	202-04°	E	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	17.16	16.97
19.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	210-11°	A	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	17.26	16.97
20.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	204°	A	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S	15.42	15.65
21.	2-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	205-06°	A+D	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S	15.24	15.55
22.	4-Methoxyphenyl	191-92°	A+D	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	15.92	16.28
23.	2,3-Dimethoxyphenyl	186-87°	D	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S	14.63	14.97
24.	2-Chlorophenyl	214-15°	A+D	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	16.34	16.07
25.	3-Chlorophenyl	190°	A	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	15.67	16.07
26.	4-Chlorophenyl	194-95°	A+D	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	15.98	16.07
27.	2-Nitrophenyl	213-15°	D	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	19.60	19.50
28.	3-Nitrophenyl	161°	E	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	19.99	19.50
29.	3,4-Dioxymethylenephenyl	192°	D	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	15.15	15.64
30.	2-Furyl	227°	A+D+?	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	17.99	16.43
III. R ₁ = 3, 4, 5-trimethoxyphenyl						
31.	Phenyl	193°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S	14.92	14.43
32.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	223-25°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	14.23	13.87
33.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	195°	E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	13.52	13.87
34.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	198-99°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	13.48	13.87
35.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	192-94°	A+D+E	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄ S	13.24	12.90
36.	2-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	178-79°	A	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄ S	13.00	12.90
37.	2-Methoxyphenyl	190°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	13.56	13.39
38.	4-Methoxyphenyl	225-27°	D+E	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₄ S	13.32	13.39
39.	2-Chlorophenyl	135-36°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ ClS	13.63	13.25
40.	3-Chlorophenyl	215°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ ClS	13.45	13.25
41.	4-Chlorophenyl	205-06°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ ClS	13.40	13.25
42.	2-Nitrophenyl	210-12°	A	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅ S	16.49	16.14
43.	3-Nitrophenyl	222-23°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅ S	16.28	16.14
44.	3,4-Dioxymethylenephenyl	183°	A	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄ S	12.98	12.90
45.	2-Furyl	208-09°	D+E	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₄ S	14.50	14.33

*Melting points are uncorrected.

*A—Acetic acid; D—Dimethylformamide; E—95% Ethanol.
All compounds have been obtained in 50-70% yields.

Pharmacology.—All the compounds reported in this communication have been screened for their antibacterial, antitubercular, and antifungal activity. Only compounds of serial number 1, 3 and 31 (Table II) have shown antitubercular activity. Compounds of serial numbers 3 and 31 (Table II) inhibit the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇ Rv, *Mycobacterium avium* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Ravenel in a concentration of 50 µg/ml, whereas compound of serial number 1 (Table II) demonstrated activity in a concentration of 100 µg/ml.

The author is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to Dr. G. S. Sidhu for his interest shown in this work, and to Dr. W. Lewis Nobles, Professor of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, University of Mississippi, U.S. A. for his valuable comments.

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Received November 1, 1965.